

Long Term Trend Analysis of Precipitation and Temperature in Southeastern States of Mauritania

El Maalouma Sidi

*College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R.;
UNEP; Tongji Institute of Environmental for Sustainable Development,
Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R*

Guotao Peng

*College of Environmental Science and Engineering, Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R.;
UNEP; Tongji Institute of Environmental for Sustainable Development,
Tongji University, Shanghai, China P.R*

Abstract

This paper examines long-term trend analysis of precipitation and temperature in three southeastern states of Mauritania, namely, Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa. Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator method have been applied to determine if there was an increasing or decreasing trend in climate data, with their statistical significance for the period of 1967-2024 for precipitation and the period of 1967 - 2023 for min/max temperature. The study area is under a unimodal rainfall regime where it receives the main rainfall during summer season, accounting for 85% of the total rainfall. The results of the study showed a significant increase in precipitation over time for Aioun station at the rate of 20 mm per decade at 1% significance level. while there is non-significant increasing trend at other stations. In terms of seasonal precipitation, Aioun station showed a significant trend in winter, spring and summer seasons with a negative trend for winter and spring while summer showed a positive trend at rate of 15 mm per decade. By contrast, there is no trend at Néma station at a 5% significance level, similarly for kiffa station even while winter precipitation decreased over time. However, annual minimum temperature had statistically significant ($P>0.01$) increasing trend at Aioun and kiffa stations at the rate of 0.4 and 0.3°C per decade, respectively. On the other hand, annual maximum temperature showed a statistically significant increasing trend at Aioun and Néma stations at the rate of 0.3 and 0.2°C per decade, respectively. Overall min temperature increased more rapid than max temperature in the study area.

Keywords: *climate change, Mauritania, precipitation, temperature, livestock production.*

Suggested citation: Sidi, E.M., & Peng, P. (2026). Long Term Trend Analysis of Precipitation and Temperature in Southeastern States of Mauritania. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 3(3), 28-42. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2026.3(3).03

Introduction

Climate change and anthropogenic factors adversely impact the hydro-meteorological process in a continuous manner, and their effects appear in the forms of trends or sudden jumps (Şen, 2012). According to the IPCC (IPCC, 2014), the trend of global ocean and land surface temperature over the last century has revealed an increase of 0.85°C (ranging between 0.65 and 1.06°C). This

warming trend has expedited and intensified the global water cycle, resulting in severe weather events, including storms, floods, and droughts (Syed et al., 2010). In addition, the IPCC reported that (IPCC, 2023) a number of sectors have been impacted by climate change, including agriculture, livestock, and human health while the largest adverse effects were detected in many regions in Africa, Asia, Central and South America, and many other places. Moreover, evidence shows that the impacts of climate change will be high in West Africa and the Sahel. Predominantly rain-fed agriculture is highly vulnerable to climate variability (Sultan & Gaetani, 2016). Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has also recognized Mauritania as one of the most African countries very vulnerable to climate change (Solomon, 2007).

Mauritania ranks 58th out of 180 countries in terms of climate change vulnerability (Eckstein et al., 2021). The climate in the country is of the Sahelian type, characterized by a long dry season from October to May and a short-wet season from June to September (Diallo, et al., 2020). The amount of rainfall and its spatial distribution are irregular between years and sometimes even during the same year (FAO, 2005). Due to climate change the country faces considerable development challenges both in the short and long term, between 1948 and 1970 the country had seen a total of 18 droughts across all its stations (Yacoub & Tayfur, 2020). A previous study reported that drought events affect roughly 944,266 people per event and incur annual costs of about USD 192.984 million, while flood events affect around 15,794 people per event at a cost of nearly USD 1.429 million each year (Neya et al., 2023), Increasing temperatures, shifting rainfall patterns, and an increase in the frequency of extreme weather events threaten food production and disrupt traditional farming methods. The country's vulnerability is worsened by its high degree of poverty and reliance on 'climate change sensitive' sectors such as fisheries, mining, and livestock and climate trends threatening livestock-based livelihoods, agriculture remains the key factor for ensuring food security and sustaining the livelihoods of the country's population data from the World Bank found that sector still has a high influence on the gross national product (23.7% in 2018) and employment (31% in 2019) (WB, 2025). Despite this more than 40% of the population of Mauritania live in poverty, with the majority (~70%) of these people living in rural areas. The communities located in these rural areas rely on rainfall-dependent, natural resource-based livelihoods including agriculture and pastoralism (Global Environment Facility, 2018).

therefore. Local food production relied heavily on rainfall for rain-fed crops (Elmokhtar et al., 2021). The Sahelian region (rural area) of Mauritania consists of an east-to west belt of steppes and savannah grasslands lying between 150mm isohyets to the North (i.e., the southern limit of the Saharan desert) and 500mm isohyets to the South (i.e., the northern limit of the Sudanian savannah) (Diallo, et al., 2020). It occupies 11% of the total surface area of Mauritania but has about 61% of the total population distributed across seven administrative provinces: Trarza, Brakna, Gorgol, Guidimagha, Assaba (kiffa), Hodh Elgharbi (Aioun) and Hodh Echarghi (Néma) (Climate Change, 2014).

The southeastern region is one of the most vulnerable regions in Mauritania and it's the main source of livestock production. In recent decades, the region has been facing increasing pressure from climate change effects, such as increasing temperatures, more variable precipitation patterns, and more frequent extreme events, particularly for subsistence farmers, such changes have been found to impact livestock performance across many regions and are projected to have growing impacts (Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya, 2025). Predictive models broadly indicate the impact will be negative (Escarcha et al., 2018). According to (El Vilaly et al., 2021) the results of the study showed distinct interactions between climate variability and interregional migration in the rural area in the country throughout the past four decades. 702,575 individuals were documented as having participated in interregional migration in 2013, comprising 17.5 % of the total population (Castles, Miller, & Ammendola, 2005). The rural community faces a significant challenge when there are even

minor changes in rainfall patterns or intensity, as their primary source of income is agriculture which is mainly dependent on climate sensitive rain feed, For example, drier conditions experienced during the 1970s and 1980s caused rural nomadic herding communities to settle near oases or migrate to urban areas. As a result, there were substantial declines in meat production across the country and considerable losses in income for livestock herders (Global Environment Facility, 2018). Since the 1950s, livestock farming in Mauritania has been highly susceptible to drought, especially affecting cattle, whose population declined by roughly one-third between 1969 and 1975. Drought-induced shortages of fodder have also led to decreased livestock productivity. During severe periods of feed scarcity, animals experience stunted growth and significant weight loss.

In spite of that several efforts have been made to examine the precipitation trends in the country during the last decades, However, there is limited empirical evidence on the long-term trends and patterns of these climatic variables. The absence of such data-based analyses hinders adaptation and policy planning. no comprehensive research has been conducted to determine the precipitation/temperature variability in this region.

There are few studies of trends of meteorological variables in the country, (Yacoub & Tayfur, 2019) studied the Trend analysis of annual temperature and precipitation time series at southern stations, the results indicate an increase in maximum, minimum, and average temperature values between 1970 and 2013 in (Trarza area), while the rainfall trends revealed an increase of 2.93 and 3.35 mm/year (Mersin, et al., 2022). (Ahmedou et al., 2008) applied the original Mann–Kendall test to detect trends in rainfall time series at three meteorological stations in northern country the results indicated a significant decreasing trend for Akjoujt station and an insignificant trend for the other stations.

Therefore, the current study seeks to analyze long-term variability in precipitation and temperature, to detect the trends of annual and seasonal over the southeastern region states of Mauritania, using the Mann–Kendall test and the Sen’s slope estimator.

The findings are expected to increase understanding of regional climate dynamics in the Sahel region, and inform policymakers and experts to develop the essential adaptation and mitigation strategies, especially in the agricultural sector.

Materials and Methods

The Study Area and Data

The southeastern states of Mauritania were selected for the present study (Figure 1). the dominant activities in the area are mainly dependent on climate sensitive rain feed agriculture, (crop and livestock production). The area is the main source of livestock production , representing approximately 56.67% of the total livestock population with 15.559 million head, including sheep (62.87%), cattle (60.65 %), camels (49.20%), and goats (24.21%) (ME, 2024). Regarding rainfall, the study area site under a single rainy season (unimodal rainfall regime) known locally as "Lekharive" which extends from June to September, and a long dry season which extends from October to May. The region makes up a combined area of 269,900 km², representing 26.19% of the country's total area.

For this study, long-term data on various climatic parameters, such as monthly minimum and maximum temperatures and rainfall, were collected from the Mauritanian National Meteorological Agency. Average annual precipitation data from 3 stations (Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa) were analyzed ,The annual rainfall at three selected stations across the regions is 237.83 mm, equivalent to around 64.2 billion m³ and the mean annual rainfall received in the study area ranges between 112.73 mm

and 401.53 mm. (Table 1) summarizes the geographic location and annual rainfall characteristics for each station, The station of Néma recorded the lowest mean of total annual precipitation at 220.7 mm, while the station of kiffa recorded the highest mean of total annual precipitation 269.7 during the period (1967-2024) According to Table 1.

Table 1. Location and Descriptive Statistics of Annual Rainfall (1967-2024)

Stations	Location		Alt(m)	Annual rainfall				
	Lat	Long		Mean(mm)	Std.Dev	Skew	Kurtosis	CV (%)
Aioun	16.66	-9.62	223	223.15	78.75	0.62	0.42	35.29
Néma	16.61	-7.26	269	220.7	82.49	0.55	0.41	37.38
Kiffa	16.62	-11.40	115	269.7	108.83	0.62	-0.40	40.35

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area

Mann–Kendall Test

The non-parametric Mann-Kendall (MK) test ((Mann, 1945) ;(Kendall, 1975)) was used for the trend identification for a given time series of data to assess the existence of monotonic trends in climatic parameters at study area during the study period using RStudio version 2025.09.1 (Posit Software, PBC) with (the ‘trend’ package version 1.1.6) , according to this test the null hypothesis H_0 and the alternative hypothesis H_a , pertain to absence or presence of trend.

In recent years , a large number of researchers have examined trend detection in hydro-meteorological time series data , using Mann Kendall test for instance (Asfaw et al., 2018) studied the trends in rainfall and temperature over Woleka sub-basin in Ethiopia from 1982 to 2015 using Mann–Kendall (MK) test and reported that the result revealed increasing trend for mean and minimum average temperatures through time significantly while the trend for maximum temperature exhibited a non-significant increasing trend (Abera, et al., 2019). (Das & Bhattacharya, 2018) used the Mann-Kendall and Sen’s method to detect rainfall and temperature trends using long-term (1980–2015) data in the west Bengal (India), whereby decreasing trends were observed in annual rainfall (- 14.31 mm year⁻¹) and annual rainy days also (- 0.63 days year⁻¹), increasing trends were detected in annual minimum and mean temperature at the rate of 0.14 and 0.05 C year⁻¹ respectively. Additionally , the Mann Kendall test and the Sen’s estimator test has been applied to observe the significant trend of perception and temperature over Tripura for the period 1969–

2014 (Tomar et al., 2017). The result observed that maximum, minimum and mean temperature over two stations of Tripura has been increased through the year except in the winter months of January and December where significant decreasing trends were observed (Das, & Bhattacharya, 2018).

The Mann–Kendall test S statistic was determined using the formula:

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sign}(x_j - x_k) \quad (1)$$

where the annual values in years j and k, respectively, are refer to x_j and x_k , with

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } (x_j - x_k) > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } (x_j - x_k) = 0 \\ -1, & \text{if } (x_j - x_k) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

in cases When the sample size "n" is greater than 10, the S statistic is considered as asymptotically, $E(s) = 0$ expressed the mean of test statistic (S), and the variance calculated by following equation:

$$\text{Var}(S) = \frac{n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{l=1}^m t_l(t_l-1)(2t_l+5)}{18} \quad (3)$$

Z, the standard normal variate, is calculated using the formula below:

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{var}(S)}} & S > 0 \\ 0 & S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{var}(S)}} & S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

to determine statistically significant trend Z value was used. At α significance level, there is no significant trend in case of $Z < Z\alpha/2$ and statistically significance trend in case of $Z \geq Z\alpha/2$ which is comes from the standard normal distribution table(Pearson & Hartley, 1966)

In this study, $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%, $Z = \pm 1.96$), with confidence levels have been used. Hence, If the Z statistic from Mann–Kendall test is under -1.96 or higher than 1.96 , then the trend is statistically significant.

Sen's Slope Estimator

Sen's slope method (Theil, 1950) , (Sen, 1968) is another non-parametric method for trend analysis of climatic data set, determined with the formula below:

$$S_i = (x_j - x_k) / (j - k) \quad (5)$$

where x_j and x_k are data values at time j and k , respectively. In the equation above $j > k$, the median of these n values of S_i is represented by Sen's slope of estimation (true slope) in $S_i = x_j - x_k / (j - k)$ (5), the S_i values are gained in ascending order, and the median value (SSmedian) is determined based on the change of the corresponding observations over time. An increasing trend is shown by positive the median value, while a negative value indicates a decreasing trend.

Analysis Tools

RStudio version 2025.09.1 (Posit Software, PBC) with (i.e. the 'modifiedmk' package version 1.6) has been used for determined Mann–Kendall Trend Test and Sen's Slope estimator to identified the trend analysis of perception and temperature while Microsoft Excel was used to manage the descriptive statistical techniques like mean, SD, coefficient of variation (CV), percent, trendline graph, and average annual rainfall and temperature graphs. The analyzed data was used to detect the trend of climate parameters across the study area.

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics of Precipitation and Temperature

During The basic statistics analysis, the mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation (CV) were calculated for the three stations in the study area. The results of the Descriptive statistics of monthly temperature are shown in . The Annual average minimum Temperature varied within the range of 22–35°C, 23–26°C, and 20–25°C at Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa, and averaged 24.26, 24.76, and 23.06°C at the respective states. Annual average Temperature maximum varied from 35 to 40°C at Aioun and Néma stations and from 35 to 39°C at kiffa station, averaging 36.5, 37, and 37.1°C at stations Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa, respectively

shows The long-term trend graphs in Tmin and Tmax at Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa during the study period.

(Appendix) indicate that the region experienced less to infrequent rainfall, even during the rainy season which in the region extends from June to September (unimodal rainfall regime). The highest rainfall was received during July and August, followed by September, for all selected stations, contributing approximately (85.18%, 85.96%, and 85.17%) of the total rainfall in the stations Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa respectively. The Coefficient of Variance was lowest in kiffa station during these months. The highest average rainfall, 254.7 mm, was recorded in August 2003 at the Néma station. while the highest average annual rainfall reached was 488.6 mm in 2024. 450.6 mm in 2003, and 534.302 mm in 1969, in stations (Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa) respectively. Using a linear regression model (see Figure 2), the rate of change is determined by the slope of the regression line, which, in the present case is around 1.7301 mm/year, 0.7268 mm/year, and 0.835 mm/year for the Aioun, Kiffa, and Néma rainfall, respectively. The rising trend for Aioun and Kiffa stations was observed to be statistically significant while that of Néma was non-significant (

Table 2) However, the regression results showed that the average annual perception in Aioun station and Kiffa station increased by 17 and 8 mm/decade, respectively, with the result being statistically significant at the 5% and 1% significance levels respectively (see

Table 2 and

).

From the last 57 years (1967–2023), data analysis shows that the min temperature ranges from 15.29°C C in January to 30.13°C in June for all the selected stations of the study area. and the coefficient of variation is highest in December (98.59%) and its lowest in June (3.668%) indicates that December rainfall is extremely variable and unreliable (

Figure 2. Annual Trends of Precipitation (1967-2024)

Table 3), while the coefficient of variation for maximum temperature is highest in August (10.942 %) and is lowest in June (1.917%). so, June experiences stable temperatures compared to other months. However, May is the hottest month of the year in the study area at all selected stations, with mean maximum temperature shoots up to as high as around 43°C (

Table 4). The lowest maximum temperature was recorded at the Aioun station in January, at 29°C. Analysis of average monthly data shown that the Aioun and Néma stations recorded the highest average maximum temperatures of 46.5°C in 2023. The Annual average minimum Temperature varied within the range of 22-35°C, 23–26°C, and 20–25°C at Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa, and averaged 24.26, 24.76, and 23.06°C at the respective states. Annual average Temperature maximum varied from 35 to 40°C at Aioun and Néma stations and from 35 to 39°C at kiffa station, averaging 36.5, 37, and 37.1°C at stations Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa, respectively

shows The long-term trend graphs in Tmin and Tmax at Aioun, Néma, and Kiffa during the study period.

Table 2. Linear Regression Annual Precipitation (1967–2024)

Station	Change in rainfall (mm/ year)	p value	R ²	CV %
Aioun	1.7301	0.0036	0.1376	35.29
Néma	0.7268	0.390	0.0221	37.38
Kiffa	0.835	0.124	0.0168	40.35

Figure 2. Annual Trends of Precipitation (1967-2024)

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Monthly Min Temperature (1967–2023)

	Aioun			Néma			Kiffa		
Month	Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV
January	16.3	2.061	12.63	17.93	1.861	10.378	15.29	2.079	13.592
February	18.80	1.663	8.84	20.48	1.723	8.416	17.61	2.206	12.525
March	22.03	1.758	7.97	23.49	1.710	7.281	20.88	2.027	9.708
April	26.06	1.716	6.58	27.00	2.020	7.481	24.48	3.918	16.00
May	29.06	2.318	7.97	29.62	2.479	8.371	28.28	2.106	7.447

June	30.13	1.376	4.56	29.92	1.097	3.668	29.50	1.680	4.394
July	27.71	1.676	6.04	27.21	1.162	4.269	27.51	1.579	5.739
August	25.97	1.071	4.122	25.98	1.611	6.203	26.04	1.254	4.815
September	26.52	1.690	6.37	26.68	1.341	5.029	25.90	1.448	5.591
October	26.74	2.427	9.07	27.03	1.2042	4.453	24.52	1.696	6.914
November	21.62	1.116	5.16	22.58	4.221	18.692	20.01	1.419	7.091
December	20.11	19.828	98.59	19.11	1.772	9.272	16.69	1.673	10.028
annual	24.26	1.888	7.783	24.76	0.879	3.550	23.06	1.133	4.913

Note: **SD, standard deviation; CV, Coefficient of Variation**

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Monthly Max Temperature (1967–2023)

	Aioun			Néma			Kiffa		
Month	Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV	Mean	SD	CV
January	29.42	2.065	7.020	30.41	2.262	7.437	30.29	2.491	8.222
February	32.46	2.372	7.306	33.41	2.068	6.191	33.61	2.157	6.419
March	36.03	2.232	6.193	36.40	1.642	4.511	36.85	2.478	6.727
April	39.71	2.012	5.068	39.97	1.297	3.245	40.68	2.040	5.016
May	42.06	1.521	3.616	41.98	2.029	4.835	42.62	1.366	3.206
June	41.96	1.055	2.516	41.78	0.801	1.917	42.36	1.089	2.570
July	38.96	1.641	4.212	38.61	1.300	3.268	38.77	1.241	3.202
August	36.14	1.689	4.673	37.34	4.086	10.942	36.85	1.581	4.292
September	37.57	1.375	3.661	38.54	1.748	4.535	37.38	1.227	3.283
October	38.36	1.689	4.403	39.17	1.6453	4.199	38.74	1.539	3.972
November	34.92	1.683	4.820	35.60	1.563	4.392	35.86	1.262	3.519
December	30.71	2.675	8.710	31.09	2.120	6.818	31.16	1.835	5.890
annual	36.53	1.061	2.906	37.03	0.951	2.570	37.10	0.819	2.209

Note: **SD, standard deviation; CV, Coefficient of Variation**

Figure 3. Annual Trends Min, Max Temperature (1967-2023)

Rainfall Trend Analysis Results

Over the last five decades and half the mean monthly rainfall over southeastern region of Mauritania during the period 1967–2024 has shown a wide variation in its occurrence. Notably, only 2 months (July and August) have accounted for around 60% of total annual rainfall in the selected stations in the study area. The total annual rainfall of the study area has varied from 113

to 401 mm, the area is characterized by a bimodal rainfall regime, with maximum rainfall concentration during rainy season which extends from June to September.

The results of the Mann–Kendall test for observed rainfall at the seasonal and annual level were given in (Table 6 - Appendix). Aioun station showed a significant trend in seasonal rainfall in winter, spring and summer seasons that found a negative trend for winter and spring while summer was found positive trend at a rate of 15 mm per decade, the significance level was 1% for winter and summer seasons, and 5% for spring season. By contrast, there is no trend in seasonal rainfall at Néma station at a 95% confidence level, similarly for kiffa station even while winter rainfall decreases over the period studied.

The results in annual rainfall shown revealed that there is non-significant increasing trend at Néma and kiffa stations at the rate of 5.5 and 14.6 mm per decade while Aioun station shows a significant increasing trend at the rate of 20 mm per decade at 99% confidence level. According to (El Vilaly et al., 2021) the results of the study showed distinct interactions between climate variability and interregional migration in the rural area in the country. while more variable rainfall can degrade rangelands over time, reduce forage quality, and increase drought frequency (Izaurrealde et al., 2011)

Temperature Trend Analysis Result

The Mann–Kendall test and the Sen slope estimator were applied to time series data from 1967 to 2023. Annual and monthly temperature data were used to detect trends in temperature change in the study area. (.

Table 7 - Appendix) shows the annual and monthly temperatures (minimum and maximum) and their trends at the selected study stations.

The monthly minimum temperature has shown, the highest Sen slope results at Aioun station were observed in April, this is not in agreement with the results of the M–K test that showed that the most significant trend appears in October (Danandeh Mehr, et al., 2021). And showed a significant ($P>0.01$) increasing trend in minimum temperature for all the months except January, February and December ,while for the Néma station there is an increasing trend in months of August and October for significance level at 0.05 contrary to highest Sen slope results which were observed in December, kiffa station showed a significant rising trend in all months except July, August, September and October for significance level at 0.01 and showed a significant trend in January and June for significance level at 0.05 this is in agreement with the results of the Sen slope test that showed that the most significant trend appears in April .

The trend for monthly maximum temperature was to be increasing at Aioun station for all the months except February, August, and September at a 99% level of significance whereas January and December at the 95% level of confidence. Néma station showed a non-significant increasing trend (except for the months of August, September, October and December at 95% level of confidence), similarly kiffa station showed a non-significant increasing trend (except for the months of April and June) at 99% level of significance. There was a significant increasing trend ($p>0.01$) for annual minimum temperature at Aioun and kiffa stations at the rate of 0.4 and 0.3° C per decade respectively, On the contrary there is non-significant trend at Néma station. maximum temperature showed statistically significant increasing trend at Aioun and Néma stations at the rate of 0.3 and 0.2° C per decade respectively, while the increase was not observed to be significant at 5% level of significance at kiffa station. The overall increase in annual temperature observed in the study area is attributed to an increase in the minimum temperature (the increment of the minimum temperature is more pronounced than the maximum) (Eshetu, et al., 2017). (Yacoub & Tayfur,

2019) also reported that the southern stations in the country showed an increase of average temperature was affected by the minimum temperature more than the maximum temperature.

The significant rise in temperature indicates warming across seasons or years, mainly affects evapotranspiration, soil degradation, and heat stress for both crops and animals (Sun et al., 2019)

Conclusion

In this present study, the Mann–Kendall and Sen slope trend test were used to detect the trend by using historical meteorological (precipitation and temperature) data, the tests are applied at 3 stations in Aioun, Néma, and, kiffa in the southeastern states of Mauritania for a period of 1967–2024 for rainfall data and from 1967-2023 for temperature data.

The study area is under a unimodal rainfall regime where it receives the main rainfall during summer season, the area receiving very little to scarce rainfall which is also unevenly distributed within the whole area. The mean rainfall for 58 years in the study area accounts for 85% of the total rainfall in the selected stations. The Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator results found that there is a statistically significant trend-for seasonal rainfall in winter, spring and summer seasons at Aioun station that found a negative trend for winter and spring while summer was found to be positive at rate of 15 mm per decade. by contrast, there is no trend in seasonal rainfall at Néma station at a 95% confidence of level, The same trend is observed for kiffa station even while winter rainfall decreases over time. Besides this, there is a statistically significant increasing trend at 99% confidence level in annual rainfall at Aioun station at the rate of 20 mm per decades and non – significant increasing trend at Néma and kiffa stations during the period (1967-2024)

In terms of temperature, we found that May is the hottest month of the year in the study area at all selected stations, with mean maximum temperature shooting up to as high as around 43°C. and June experienced stable temperatures compared to other months. Mann–Kendall test and Sen’s slope estimator Results showed that for min temperature there is a significant increasing trends during the hot and dry part of the year, from march to December at Aioun station, there was an increasing trend in month of August, September, October and December for significance level at 0.05 showed at Néma station, kiffa station showed a significant increasing trend in all months except July, August, September and October for significance level at 0.01 and showed significant trend in January and June for significance level at 0.05. annual minimum temperature had statistically significant ($P>0.01$) increasing trend at Aioun and kiffa stations at the rate of 0.4 and 0.3° C per decade respectively, On the contrary there is non-significant trend at Néma station. On the other hand, annual maximum temperature showed statistically significant increasing trend at Aioun and Néma stations at the rate of 0.3 and 0.2° C per decade respectively, and non – significant increasing trend at kiffa station, overall min temperature increased more rapid than max temperature at the study area.

Within the vulnerable Sahelian ecosystem, increasing temperature and erratic rainfall will lead to enhancement of drought, which is very expected to affect land degradation and desertification, crop varieties, and consequent agricultural productivity which is the main source of food, feed, and fibre for both humans and animals. This study presents the trend analysis of temperature and rainfall which can help to understand regional climatology and hydrology and their effects on sectors based on water incomes. The results expected to help policymakers and experts develop the essential adaptation and mitigation strategies for the impacts of climate change in Mauritania.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

References

- Abera, F., Asfaw, D., Nigussie, A., & Melesse, A. (2019). Precipitation and streamflow variability in Tekeze River Basin, Ethiopia. *Hydrology: Current Research*, 10(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7587.1000320>
- Ahmedou, O., Yasuda, H., Wang, K., & Hattori, K. (2008). Characteristics of precipitation in northern Mauritania and its links with sea surface temperature. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 72(12), 2243–2250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2008.07.011>
- Asfaw, A., Simane, B., Hassen, A., & Bantider, A. (2018). Variability and time series trend analysis of rainfall and temperature in northcentral Ethiopia: A case study in Woleka sub-basin. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 19, 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2017.12.002>
- Castles, S., Miller, M., & Ammendola, G. (2005). The age of migration: International population movements in the modern world. *American Foreign Policy Interests*, 27(4), 315–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10803920500434037>
- Danandeh Mehr, A., Hrnjica, B., Bonacci, O., & Haghghi, A. T. (2021). Innovative and successive average trend analysis of temperature and precipitation in Osijek, Croatia. *Theoretical and Applied Climatology*, 145(3–4), 875–890. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-021-03672-3>
- Das, J., & Bhattacharya, S. K. (2018). Trend analysis of long-term climatic parameters in Dinhat of Koch Bihar district, West Bengal. *Spatial Information Research*, 26(3), 271–280. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41324-018-0173-3>
- Diallo, S. M., Bogreau, H., Papa Mze, N., Ould Ahmedou Salem, M. S., Ould Khairy, M. L., Parola, P., Basco, L., & Ould Mohamed Salem Boukhary, A. (2020). Malaria epidemiology in Kobeni department, southeastern Mauritania from 2015 to 2017. *Infectious Diseases of Poverty*, 9(1), Article 21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40249-020-0634-5>
- Eckstein, D., Künzel, V., Schäfer, L., & Winges, M. (2021). *Global climate risk index 2021: Who suffers most from extreme weather events (2000–2019)*. Germanwatch.
- El Vilaly, M. A. S., Jones, M., Tankari, M. R., Mahé, G., & Juran, S. (2021). Mauritania's internal migration dynamics and trends in response to rainfall variability and change. *Statistical Journal of the LAOS*, 37(4), 1139–1153. <https://doi.org/10.3233/SJI-210815>
- Elmokhtar, A., Saleck, A., Ajjane, A., Zamel, M., & Tounkara, H. (2021). Pedo-agronomic and environmental analysis of some agricultural soils of Keur-Macene south of Mauritania. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology*, 12(3), 298–310. <https://doi.org/10.34218/IJARET.12.3.2021.030>
- Escarcha, J. F., Lassa, J. A., & Zander, K. K. (2018). Livestock under climate change: A systematic review of impacts and adaptation. *Climate*, 6(3), Article 54. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli6030054>
- Eshetu, A., Simane, B., Hassen, A., & Bantider, A. (2017). Variability and time series trend analysis of rainfall and temperature in northcentral Ethiopia: A case study in Woleka sub-basin. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 19, 29–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wace.2017.12.002>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2005). *Mauritania country profile*. Retrieved January 22, 2026, from http://www.fao.org/nr/water/aquastat/countries_regions/mrt/indexfra.stm

- Global Environment Facility. (2018). *Climate change adaptation and livelihoods in three arid regions of Mauritania*. <https://www.thegef.org>
- Government of Mauritania, Ministry of Livestock. (2024). *A special issue on the general census of livestock*. <http://www.elevage.gov.mr>
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2014). *Summary for policymakers*. In *Climate change 2014: Impacts, adaptation, and vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report*. Cambridge University Press.
- Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. (2023). *Summary for policymakers*. In *Climate change 2023: Synthesis report*. IPCC.
- Islamic Republic of Mauritania, Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development. (2014). *Third national communication to the UNFCCC*. <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/natc/mrtnc3.pdf>
- Izaurrealde, R. C., Thomson, A. M., Morgan, J., Fay, P., Polley, H., & Hatfield, J. L. (2011). Climate impacts on agriculture: Implications for forage and rangeland production. *Agronomy Journal*, 103(2), 371–381. <https://doi.org/10.2134/agronj2010.0304>
- Kendall, M. G. (1975). *Rank correlation methods* (2nd ed.). Hafner Press.
- Malik, A., Kumar, A., Guhathakurta, P., et al. (2019). Spatial-temporal trend analysis of seasonal and annual rainfall (1966–2015) using innovative trend analysis method with significance test. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 12, Article 328. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12517-019-4454-5>
- Mann, H. B. (1945). Nonparametric tests against trend. *Econometrica*, 13(3), 245–259. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1907187>
- Mersin, D., Tayfur, G., Vaheddoost, B., & Safari, M. J. S. (2022). Historical trends associated with annual temperature and precipitation in Aegean Turkey: Where are we heading? *Sustainability*, 14(20), Article 13380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013380>
- Neya, T., Abunyewa, A. A., Kiribou, R., Neya, O., Magistro, J., Soubeiga, J., Kiemde, P., Semde, M., & Gadjaga, K. (2023). Disaster risk profile analysis for better decision on climate financing instrument in Mauritania. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 13(9), 1545–1557. <https://doi.org/10.9734/IJECC/2023/v13i92386>
- Pearson, E. S., & Hartley, H. O. (1966). *Biometrika tables for statisticians* (Vol. 1, 3rd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Sen, P. K. (1968). Estimates of the regression coefficient based on Kendall's tau. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 63(324), 1379–1389. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1968.10480934>
- Şen, Z. (2012). Innovative trend analysis methodology. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, 17(9), 1042–1046. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)HE.1943-5584.0000556](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)HE.1943-5584.0000556)
- Solomon, S. (Ed.). (2007). *Climate change 2007: The physical science basis*. Cambridge University Press.
- Sultan, B., & Gaetani, M. (2016). Agriculture in West Africa in the twenty-first century: Climate change and impacts scenarios, and potential for adaptation. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 7, Article 1262. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2016.01262>
- Sun, Q., Miao, C., Hanel, M., Borthwick, A. G. L., Duan, Q., Ji, D., & Li, H. (2019). Global heat stress on health, wildfires, and agricultural crops under different levels of climate warming. *Environment International*, 128, 125–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.04.025>

- Syed, T. H., Famiglietti, J. S., Chambers, D. P., Willis, J. K., & Hilburn, K. (2010). Satellite-based global-ocean mass balance estimates of interannual variability and emerging trends in continental freshwater discharge. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(42), 17916–17921. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1003292107>
- Theil, H. (1950). A rank-invariant method of linear and polynomial regression analysis (Part 3). *Proceedings of the Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen, Series A*, 53, 1397–1412.
- Tomar, C., Saha, D., Das, S., Shaw, S., Bist, S., & Gupta, M. (2017). Analysis of temperature variability and trends over Tripura. *Mausam*, 68(1), 149–160. <https://doi.org/10.54302/mausam.v68i1.444>
- Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya. (2025). *ICAR sponsored winter school on “Impact of climate change on agriculture and allied sector: Adaptation, mitigation towards sustainability and livelihood security” (February 14–March 6, 2025): Training manual*. Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya.
- Waqas, M., Wannasingha Humphries, U., & Hlaing, P. T. (2024). Time series trend analysis and forecasting of climate variability using deep learning in Thailand. *Results in Engineering*, 24, Article 102997. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.102997>
- World Bank. (2025). *Climate Change Knowledge Portal – Mauritania*. <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/mauritania/vulnerability>
- Yacoub, E., & Tayfur, G. (2019). Trend analysis of temperature and precipitation in Trarza region of Mauritania. *Journal of Water and Climate Change*, 10(3), 484–493. <https://doi.org/10.2166/wcc.2018.007>
- Yacoub, E., & Tayfur, G. (2020). Spatial and temporal variation of meteorological drought and precipitation trend analysis over whole Mauritania. *Journal of African Earth Sciences*, 163, Article 103761. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2020.103761>

Appendix

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Monthly Precipitation in mm (1967–2024)

Month	Aioun			%	Néma			%	Kiffa			%
	Mean	SD	CV		Mean	SD	CV		Mean	SD	CV	
January	0.869	4.1856	481.56	0.39	0.274	1.5204	554.52	0.12	0.386	1.619	419.12	0.14
February	0.123	0.6121	499.56	0.06	0.339	2.4151	711.02	0.15	0.343	1.616	471.16	0.13
March	0.516	2.2235	1812.59	0.23	0.044	0.2153	479.82	0.02	0.300	1.202	400.70	0.11
April	1.628	4.5379	278.78	0.73	2.332	7.1770	307.65	1.06	0.463	2.392	515.84	0.17
May	2.845	6.3993	224.93	1.27	3.486	6.0827	174.47	1.58	3.822	11.68	305.70	1.42
June	13.517	20.6927	153.08	6.06	13.898	16.711	120.23	6.30	18.160	19.413	106.90	6.73
July	52.371	34.3703	65.62	23.47	54.127	30.990	57.25	24.53	59.908	44.162	73.71	22.21
August	92.959	44.4190	47.78	41.66	90.391	53.561	59.25	40.96	102.44	49.581	48.39	37.99
September	44.734	28.2245	63.09	20.05	45.175	38.169	84.49	20.47	67.339	53.905	80.05	24.97
October	12.285	18.3576	149.43	5.51	9.524	18.294	192.08	4.32	13.627	26.973	197.93	5.05
November	0.497	1.8648	375.48	0.22	0.601	2.714	451.05	0.27	1.025	5.097	496.90	0.38
December	0.805	2.9708	368.97	0.36	0.489	1.708	348.77	0.22	1.863	7.592	407.43	0.69

Table 6. Annual Trends of Precipitation (1967-2024)

Season	Rainfall								
	Aioun			Néma			Kiffa		
	Z Mk	Sen slope	trend	Z Mk	Sen slope	trend	Z Mk	Sen slope	trend
Winter	-2.7259**	-0.00002	Yes (-)	-1.906	0.0000	No (-)	-2.2494*	0.000	Yes (-)
Spring	-2.2929*	-0.01133	Yes (-)	-1.803	-0.00007	No (-)	0.4527	0.000	No (+)
Summer	3.3205**	1.57575	Yes (+)	1.5630	0.60952	No (+)	1.8581	1.110	No (+)
Autumn	1.3483	0.3499	No (+)	0.1073	0.0533	No (+)	-0.067	-0.028	No (-)
annual	2.9046**	2.0092	Yes (+)	0.8586	0.5464	No (+)	1.5362	1.4589	No (+)

Note: * Statistically significant trends at the 0.05 level and ** Statistically significant at the 0.05, and 0.01 level respectively.

Table 7. Trend Statistics of Minimum and Maximum Monthly Temperature (1967-2023)

Month	T min						T max					
	Aioun		Néma		Kiffa		Aioun		Néma		Kiffa	
	Z Mk	Q	Z Mk	Q	Z Mk	Q	Z Mk	Q	Z Mk	Q	Z Mk	Q
January	1.570	0.025	1.033	0.016	2.128*	0.038	2.017*	0.035	1.377	0.027	-0.268	-0.0038
February	1.818	0.027	0.00	0.00	2.713**	0.055	1.184	0.022	0.743	0.011	-0.006	0.00
March	3.692**	0.046	0.881	0.015	2.790**	0.044	3.135**	0.05	-0.158	0.00	1.219	0.025
April	5.269**	0.069	0.137	0.00	4.311**	0.083	5.522**	0.075	1.268	0.015	4.215**	0.052
May	4.966**	0.068	0.165	0.001	3.232**	0.047	5.59**	0.062	1.730	0.02	1.764	0.017
June	5.612**	0.048	0.875	0.008	2.088*	0.022	4.912**	0.042	1.400	0.01	2.709**	0.025
July	4.651**	0.055	1.413	0.014	0.661	0.006	2.914**	0.036	1.068	0.013	1.200	0.009
August	3.467**	0.028	1.963*	0.024	-0.027	0.00	0.634	0.007	0.778	0.011	1.674	0.020
September	4.261**	0.034	2.35*	0.027	1.887	0.02	1.846	0.020	1.598	0.020	-1.295	-0.013
October	7.179**	0.068	2.012*	0.022	1.604	0.025	4.644**	0.05	2.811*	0.025	-0.716	-0.009
November	3.330**	0.028	0.434	0.007	2.626**	0.029	3.651**	0.045	3.664**	0.05	1.682	0.016
December	2.362*	0.036	2.562*	0.035	3.590**	0.047	1.955	0.037	2.816**	0.043	0.309	0.003
annual	6.52**	0.044	1.521	0.012	3.35**	0.029	5.094**	0.033	2.822**	0.0195	1.7075	0.0107

Note: *Significant at 5%. **Significant at 5% and 1%. level respectively

